

**THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ROLE OF ECONOMETRIC MODELING IN
THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS IN THE REGIONS**

Aminova N.B.

*Aminova Niginabonu Bakhriddinovna – teacher of
Department of Economics,
Bukhara State University, Bukhara, Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Abstract: *This article presents opinions about the role and importance of econometric modeling in the development of transport logistics in the regions. Rapid changes in the transport-logistics market in the conditions of digital globalization require constant study of new trends in development. Some aspects of the formation of the modern international transport-logistics system are revealed in the works of foreign and domestic authors.*

Keywords: *transport logistics, econometric modeling, transport services, transport system.*

Today, the main requirements in the development of logistics are an in-depth study of demand using the transport balance of the regions, increasing the quality and reliability of customer service, improving the complex of loading and unloading and storage works, providing information and forwarding services, strengthening contractual relations, developing services, establishment of various associations, joint-stock companies, leasing companies, etc., which are members of enterprises, delivery of rolling stock, creation of intermediate firms for logistics, marketing, advertising, distribution of container use.

European economist A. Burda expressed the role of logistics services in the economy with the following objectives. Currently, one of the most important issues in the export practice of the country's national economy is logistics services, which are considered by the leaders of the food industry, horticulture, leather industry, textile industry, cotton and other manufacturing enterprises.

In the traditional system, we had to carry a lot of inventory in foreign countries to meet customer needs and provide excellent customer service.

The following proposals and actions are important in the development of transport logistics:

Infrastructure Development: Modern and efficient infrastructure is required for good transport logistics. Development of road networks, railways, airways and rivers, adding new connections and maintaining them are fundamental to providing an efficient transport system.

Study and application of modern technologies: Integration of modern technologies in transport logistics, automation of road and network systems, improvement of underground vehicles and introduction of monitoring systems are important in the development of an efficient transport system.

Improving logistics services: Increasing efficiency in the provision of logistics services, delivery and warehousing (Improving storage processes in warehouses, reforming the transport system is important in the development of logistics.

International commercial partnerships: International commercial partnerships are also important in the development of transport logistics. The impact of trade between countries on other sectors, the integration of transport into international systems will help to make changes.

Interactions and collaborations: It is also important to develop interactions and collaborations between entities in the field of transport. It is important to study inclusion, consultation and other collaborations instead of multilateral relations between entrepreneurs, government and other organizations.

Personnel training and motivation: For the development of transport logistics, personnel with good training and professional experience are needed. It is very important to organize this process well, motivate and develop personnel, and provide training to learn new technologies.

Political support and guarantees: States should provide political decisions

and guarantees in the development of transport logistics. Investments, legal protections and other state political measures are important in the development of transport logistics.

Effective Monitoring and Analysis: It is important to build effective monitoring and analysis systems to effectively monitor transportation system services, improve compliance, and manage bids. These suggestions should be implemented in practice and their results should be analyzed, then necessary changes should be made and development should continue.

Transport services constitute an important part of the volume of export of services in many national economies. As an example, the Republic of Belarus is a country located at the crossroads of transport routes connecting the CIS countries with the European Union and the People's Republic of China, as well as the countries on the Black Sea coast with the Baltic Sea countries.

Effective use of the international potential of transport logistics, search for ways to increase the export of transport services is a priority economic task. Consequently, the development of economic-mathematical means of forecasting the export of transport services and the identification of factors that significantly affect it are an important and urgent scientific problem for our country.

Theoretical issues and practice of organization of cross-border logistics systems, their functional activities are discussed by famous foreign authors D.J. Bowersox, L.B. Mirotina, Yu.M. Nerusha, Yu.I. Rizhikova, V.I. Sergeeva, T. Vaytina and others. R.B. in their work, they focused on some issues of forecasting in the field of transport and logistics. Ivut, A.A. Surkov, T.A. Tkalich, A.A. Frenkel, A.V. Shurubovich. However, there are still no accurate models for forecasting the export of transport services in the Territories, which are an important element of the country's balance of payments.

Econometric forecasting and modeling should fill this gap and provide tools for forecasting the export of freight services in the context of the general and its types (rail, road, pipeline). Forecast values of export of transport services make

it possible to determine their contribution to the growth of the country's gross domestic product, identify emerging problems and ways to solve them.

Thus, improving the theoretical foundations of transport logistics, determining its international potential, creating models for forecasting the export of cargo transportation services, and regions are of scientific, theoretical, and practical importance. The relevance of the identified problems, their insufficient development and high socio-economic importance for the regions determine the choice of the goals and structure of the development of this area.

A new approach to transportation, which today appears as a component of a larger system, covering all aspects of the cargo transportation process, i.e., the flow of information in the shipment, reception, processing, packaging, storage, placement and delivery of cargo. made it possible to conclude that the review is appropriate.

Unlike the transport system, which includes a complex of various types of transport related to and cooperating with the implementation of cargo transportation, the integrated transport-logistics system ensures that time and costs are brought to a minimum level. The transport-logistics system means "consumers and service providers, as well as users of the management system for them, means of transport, information roads, structures and other properties are understood."

Integrated transport-logistics system is understood as a general management set of integrated transport and logistics infrastructures, transport enterprises and vehicles. As any system consists of certain complex elements that are interconnected and interact, the integrated transport-logistics system also includes a number of complex systems.

According to the principles of the systematic approach calculated from the scientific approaches of management, the integrated transport-logistics system can be described as a complex and, in itself, ineffectively managed system. In our opinion, the management of the integrated transport-logistics system is the purposeful regulation of the system by means of economic, organizational-

administrative, legal management methods and various levers by the management bodies of the transport company as an object and subject of management. The integrated transport-logistics system In order to make appropriate management decisions in effective management, the field should be regularly monitored. As the initial element of the management mechanism lies the management goal.

Defining the goal is the most responsible stage in the development and adoption of management decisions, as it determines the strategic and tactical directions of system development. In the dissertation, the management mechanism of the integrated transport-logistics system is improved based on management concepts, integrated management criteria, and integrated logistics concepts that allow synchronizing logistics operations. By using this control mechanism, it is possible to effectively organize business processes in the railway network, store goods in warehouses, control the movement of goods and increase the efficiency of its management, taking into account the continuous operation of the system. One of the important criteria for evaluating the transport system is the logistics are indicators.

If we look at the logistics efficiency index of the republic, the highest results can be seen in the indicators of infrastructure and on-time delivery. However, compared to the logistics efficiency indicators of foreign countries, they are lagging behind.

References

1. Agzamov, A. T., & Rakhmatullaeva, F. M., Giyazova N. B. (2021). Regional Aspects Of Tourism Development. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 2(6), 153-156.
2. Muhammedrisaevna, T. M., Shukrullaevich, A. F., & Bakhriddinova, A. N. (2021). The Logistics Approach In Managing A Tourism Company. *Researchjet Journal Of Analysis And Inventions*, 2(04), 231-236.

3. Tairova, M., Asadov, F., & Aminova, N. (2019). Logistics System In Tourism: Features, Functions And Opportunities. *International Finance And Accounting*, 2019(5), 16.

4. Асадов, Ф. Ш., & Аминова, Н. Б. (2020). Transportation System In Tourism Logistics. *Наука, Техника И Образование*, (6), 68-70.

5. Shukrullaevich, A. F., & Bakhriddinovna, A. N. (2020). Transportation System In Tourism Logistics. *Наука, Техника И Образование*, (6 (70)), 68-70.

6. Таирова, М. М., Асадов, Ф. Ш., & Аминова, Н. Б. (2020). Особенности Развития Устойчивого Сельского Туризма. *Вопросы Науки И Образования*, (11 (95)).

7. Tairova, M. M., Sh, A. F., & Aminova, N. B. (2020). Discussion Of Tourism Logistics Based On The Theory Of Separation And Association Of Tourists And Objects. In *European Research: Innovation In Science, Education And Technology* (Pp. 17-19).

8. Таирова, М. М., Асадов, Ф. Ш., & Аминова, Н. Б. (2020). Влияние Covid-19 На Агропродовольственные Цепочки Поставок. *Вестник Науки И Образования*, (12-2 (90)).

9. Таирова, М. М., Асадов, Ф. Ш., & Аминова, Н. Б. (2020). Influence Of Covid-19 On Agricultural Food Supply Chains. *Вестник Науки И Образования*, (12-2), 34-36.

10. Bakhriddinovna, A. N., & Qizi, K. D. R. (2020). Tourism Logistics: Relationship Between Tourism And Logistics. *Academy*, (7 (58)).

11. Muhammedrisaevna, T. M., Shukrullaevich, A. F., & Bakhriddinovna, A. N. (2021). The Importance Of Logistics In The Sphere Of Transportation And Tourist Services. *Наука И Образование Сегодня*, (5 (64)), 16-18.

12. Junaydulloevich, A. A., Bakhriddinovna, A. N., & Olimovna, R. N. Business And Product Delivery In The Context Of Covid-19.

13. Rasul Kizi-Student, K. D. (2021). Tourism Clusters Institutional Environment Kadirova Nozima Rasulovna-Student Aminova Niginabonu

Bakhriddinova-Student. *Europe, Science And We Evropa, Věda A My Ešona, Nauka I My*, 11.

14. Mukhamedova, D. G., & Abdullajanova, D. S. (2020). The Actuality Of The Gender Aspect Of The Manager's Constructive Interaction In The Conflicting Situation. *Journal Of Critical Reviews*, 7(12), 228-231.

15. Khalimova, N. J., Murotova, N. U., & Aminova, N. B. Cluster Approach In The Tourism Business.